

Interaction Information Versus Movement Information in Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

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The classical spatial density $P(x)dx = dx/L$ (where L is an arbitrary length) is independent of v (velocity) and p (momentum), i.e. from the point of view of motion, space is the same, we argue. In other words, $x=vt$ for both a classical and quantum particle (if there are no interactions) both relativistically and nonrelativistically. If this is the case, then how does quantum mechanics arise? We suggest that one must ask whether space is the same from the point of momentum. This begs the question: What is momentum? In Newtonian mechanics it is a measure of the type of interaction which occurs $dp/dt = \text{Force}$, regardless of the nature of the force (only the magnitude is relevant in one dimension). Thus, we ask: Does $P(x)dx = dx/L$, i.e. the ubiquitous nature of space apply to momentum, i.e. to interactions?

One might argue that p only acts at the point of interaction (i.e. at the location of say a target) and so should have nothing to do with space (other than this interaction location). A priori, simply because a particle moves smoothly in space via $x=vt$, this need not be the case for the momentum interaction process. Momentum represents information in space due to motion and one might argue that this should manifest itself spatially even if a hit with a target does not occur. If no hit occurs, the manifestation of momentum in space should map to $P(x)dx=dx/L$, otherwise information about the magnitude of momentum should appear. If information about momentum is to appear in space, it should be linked to both the magnitude of momentum (in 1D) and space itself, presumably in equally spaced length units if there is to be any kind of mapping back to $P(x)=\text{constant}$. This suggests a length unit which is a function of p , i.e. $f(p)$. We pursue this line of reasoning to argue that $\exp(ipx)$ then appears mathematically.

Secondly, we consider experimental results of diffraction. In both classical and quantum free particle mechanics, a particle moves as $x=vt$ and such a scenario does not imply any diffraction. If a diffraction pattern is to be produced, we suggest that there must be a spatial probability profile linked with the interaction, i.e. with the momentum of the particle. This is in keeping with an $f(p)$ inherent length for a probability region for a given p . We also investigate this scenario.

Momentum as Information in Space

Momentum is a measure of impulse (linked to force) regardless of the nature of the force. This idea holds in both Newtonian mechanics and special relativity, although in the latter, $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ (1D). In other words, momentum is information. This information is manifested when a collision occurs with say a target at a point x_0 . We ask: Should p information disappear altogether if the particle is not colliding in space?

A particle with a constant velocity v moves as $x=vt$ both classically and in quantum mechanics. $P(x)dx=dx/L$ (L is an arbitrary length) seems to hold for both with respect to motion alone. The question we ask is: Does this ubiquitous nature of space (x) also hold for interactions, i.e. for the variable p ? In other words, even though p is measured at x_0 , the location of a target, the information about p exists in all of space because the target can be at any x_0 .

One might postulate a function of p and x which maps to $P(x)=\text{constant}$ when no interaction occurs, but nevertheless carries the information of p in space. Given the invariance of space in $P(x)$ it seems that this function, if real, should be periodic in x with the period being some function $g(p)$. This, however, would suggest values of $f(g(p),x)$ which are larger than others and this violates the notion of $P(x)=\text{constant}$ for no interaction. Thus, it seems one must choose a complex function with a constant modulus, i.e.

$$\exp[i f(g(p), x)] \quad ((1))$$

((1)) still contains two unknown functions: f and g . Furthermore:

$$\exp[i f(g(p_1), x)] \exp[i f(g(p_2), x)] = \exp[i f(g(p_1+p_2), x)] \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{So } f(g(p_1), x) + f(g(p_2), x) = f(g(p_1+p_2), x) \quad ((3))$$

One could in general have:

Sum over i $G_i(p) x^{\text{power } i}$, i.e. a power expansion in x .

Given that one wishes to capture p as information, we do not consider an extra term $z(x)$ with no p coefficient. This suggests that every:

$$G_i(p_1) + G_i(p_2) = G_i(p_1+p_2) \quad ((4)) \quad \text{A solution to } ((4)) \text{ is to have } G_i(p) = p.$$

One may let $p_2=dp$ and $p_1=p$. Then: $G_i(p) + G_i(dp) = G_i(p) + G_i(0) + dp \frac{dG_i}{dp}$ at $p=0 = G_i(p) + \frac{dG_i}{dp}(p=0) dp$

This means that: $G_i(0) = 0$ or $G_i(p) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } a_i p^{\text{power } i}$ where a_i are constants. For arbitrary p in a power law, ((4)) should match $p^{\text{power } n}$ terms. Thus, only the linear p term holds.

This leaves the issue of $x^{\text{power } i}$. If one considers space to be uniform, then each dx should carry the same weight, i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \text{Sum over } i \text{ } G_i(p) x^{\text{power } i} = \text{constant and this only holds for } x^{\text{power } 1}.$$

Thus, based on informational arguments alone (we argue) one may only choose:

$\exp(ipx)$ as the probability function which carries p information.

Here we have made the assumption that $\exp(i \text{Sum over } i \text{ } G_i(p) x^{\text{power } i})$ represents the most general periodic function.

The assumption of space carrying information about p , however, seems to have unusual implications, which we consider in the next section. From a mathematical point of view we suggest that $P(x) = \text{constant}$ does not carry information about p which physically exists, but if no interaction occurs, $P(x) = \text{constant}$ is the correct result. Thus, one has a periodic nature to the impulse even though $x=vt$ is smooth. Simply because p is proportional to v both relativistically and nonrelativistically does not mean that p moves smoothly in space like v . $\exp(ipx)$ is a perfectly fine math solution, we argue. The question is whether it is linked with any physics.

The Case of Diffraction

We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ is compatible with experimental diffraction results. We only consider qualitative results because these establish the notion of a p which creates a periodicity in space based on a function $f(p)$. (It is already known in the literature that $\exp(ipx)$ produces the quantitative diffraction results.) (Here we are only interested in the notion of a nonsmooth p probability in x even though $x=vt$ is completely smooth for both quantum mechanics and Newtonian mechanics (relativistic or nonrelativistic).)

If one observes a diffraction pattern, two points to consider are:

- (a) For a given p , there is a special length \hbar/p for which diffraction appears. If the diameter of the hole is much larger than this there is no diffraction.
 - (b) A set of crests is produced which look somewhat like a periodic function (although heights are different.
- (a) Suggests that the smooth nature of $x=vt$ does not hold when the diameter reaches a certain size for a given p , namely \hbar/p . The pattern on the screen suggests probability which seems to mean that each x point in the diameter of the hole is associated with a different probability weight. $x=vt$ does not predict this, but the existence of the hole suggests an interaction with light or a particle and so p which characterizes such an interaction in a general way must be linked with a probability in x scheme, it seems. In other words, there is nothing wrong with a p linked with a probability scheme in x even if $x=vt$ is smooth quantum mechanically. Given the periodic nature of the result on the screen, one might consider two rays from each side of the circular hole and argue that a probability applies to each. The probability is then linked with a resolution length along the ray it seems.

In other word, the results of a diffraction experiment seem to justify the idea that p (linked with interactions) is information which must be manifested in space, albeit in a probabilistic manner which must map to $P(x) = \text{constant}$ in the case of no interaction. In order to distinguish between different p in space one must have length units associated with $f(p)$.

Conclusion

We argue that a p momentum describes an interaction quantitatively and is independent of the type of force (i.e. Newton's second law). Even though a collision with a target occurs at a specific x_0 point, this point could be everywhere, so we suggest that p information should exist

in space. The usual $x=vt$ equation which holds for quantum mechanics and classical mechanics, both nonrelativistically and relativistically, suggests that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ (L =arbitrary length). If a particle does interact, any function (probability type) must map to $P(x)=\text{constant}$. We argue using $P_1(x) = \exp(i \sum_n G_n(p) x^n)$ to represent a general periodic function with modulus 1 to capture $P(x)=\text{constant}$, $P_1(p_1)P_1(p_2) = P_1(p_1+p_2)$ leads to $\exp(ipx)$. This suggests that even though $x=vt$ is smooth, the interaction (impulse) p is described in a complex periodic manner in space which maps through $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. In other words, just because motion is smooth in x , an interaction need not be in x .

To test this idea of momentum being linked to space in a periodic manner, we try to qualitatively describe the results of diffraction. Quantitatively it is known that $\exp(ipx)$ describes this scenario, but we argue that qualitatively that the diffraction pattern suggests a probability linked to p (interaction) which depends on x and is periodic in nature and associated with a length \hbar/p for a given p .